

Decentralized Power Management in RF Mesh Networks for Frequency Reuse

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Introduction:

The objective of this work is to develop power control techniques to allow frequency reuse of non-spread carrier frequencies within a RF-mesh mobile topology. The HF Automatic Link Establishment (ALE) system defined in MILSTD 188-141A is a procedure by which linking to a particular addressed radio can be done automatically in a group of congested HF channels [2]. This is a distributed control algorithm to gain access of a free channel from a set of frequencies. When the radio want to call an address it will rank the channels for sequence of calling according to link quality Analysis (LQA) scores. The basic procedure is to call only if that channel is silent. That channel is dedicated to only one party of users as long as they are busy. Two radios will go through the usual request to send (RTS), clear to send (CTS), and acknowledgment (ACK) to establish a link.

The work reported here is to create a compatible algorithm that will reuse the busy channel whenever necessary. Note that in HF-ALE protocol calls are only made to a channel if it is silent. Under power management situation an initiating radio may be far from a pair of radios using minimum (non audible) power for linkage, it is necessary to use more information to decide on initiating a call on a channel even if the channel is silent. ALE radios use sounding periodically to keep up neighbor awareness.

The idea of "frequency reuse" is simple which is based on the fact that the propagation loss is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the distance. When the third and the fourth radios are

far away enough from a pair of busy radios, their channel can be reused. The power management algorithm is not aware the two dimensional positions of the radios. Through the sounding at full power and ALE message exchange relative distance estimate of neighbors can be maintained at radios. When a channel is silent without any reuse, the access to channel is done in the same way as ALE protocol. Once the channel is used, the radio gaining the channel (radio A) will assume a point control function to coordinate reuse of the channel. It will announce contention free period usage and allows channel reuse request (RR) in the polled period. To demonstrate the frequency reuse algorithms OPNET simulation were conducted. Various scenarios were developed to show the advantages.

Automatic Frequency Selection

The HF Automatic Link Establishment (ALE) system defined in appendix A of MILSTD 188-141A is a procedure by which link to a particular addressed radio can be done automatically in a group of congested HF channels. This is a distributed control algorithm to gain access of a free channel from a set of frequencies. Every ALE conforming radio plays equal role to initiate and answer to traffic calls. The operational rules are best summarized in TABLE A-XIII of the MILSTD 188-141A which is listed as follows:

1. Independent ALE receive capability
2. Always listening
3. Always respond
4. Always scanning

5. Will not interfere with active ALE channels
6. Always exchange Link Quality Analysis (LQA) messages when requested
7. Will respond in preset/derived/directed time slot
8. Always seek and maintain track of connectivity with others
9. Plays highest mutual level of capability
10. Minimize transmit and receive time of channels
11. Automatically minimize power

LQA message includes basic bit-error-rate (BER), signal-plus-noise-plus-distortion to noise-plus-distortion ratio (SINAD), and multipath (MP) fields (refers to 141A appendix A, section 60.6). when this messages are exchanged among ALE radios, a connectivity and LQA memory is maintained (refers to Fig. A-3, page 46 of STD 188-141A). It is basically a matrix of addresses of radios as rows and channels as columns. Each element contains BER, SINAD, MP, and LQA age for both to and from directions of that address. When the radio want to call an address it will rank the channels for sequence of calling according to LQA scores (refers to Fig. A-20, page 94 of STD 141A). The basic procedure is to call only if that channel is silent. Even though according to operating rule 11: power is minimized, that channel is dedicated to only one party of users as long as they are busy.

Power Management for Frequency Reuse

The key idea is to create a compatible algorithm that will reuse the busy channel whenever necessary. Note that in HF-ALE protocol calls are only made to a channel if it is silent. Under power management situation in this proposal an initiating radio may be far from a pair of radios using minimum (non audible) power for linkage, it is necessary to use more information to decide initiating a call on a channel even if the channel is silent.

Among ALE radios sounding are provided periodically to keep up neighbor awareness. This short beacon like signal can be analyzed to update LQA matrix or to initiate subsequent LQA exchange. Sounding at full power will also be used in this proposed power management algorithm.

Radio Distance Estimation

Let's assume radio A is calling radio B, and channel C2 is silent. It initiates a "To B, This is A" message which is referred to as the Request to Sent (RTS) type of message. Within the preset time radio B responds a "To A, This is B" message which is referred to as the Clear to Sent (CTS) message. Then, radio A respond a "To B, This is A" message again as an acknowledge (ACK). From that point on either PTT voice, RTTY, or other traffic can be exchanged until the end.

The idea of "frequency reuse" is simple which is based on the fact that the propagation loss is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the distance. When the third and the fourth radios are far away enough from a pair of busy radios, their channel can be reused. The complication comes from the fact of slow and fast fading phenomena associated with UHF signals. Slow fading is due to shadowing and has a variation of 4 to 10 dB. Fast fading can have a large variation range of 26 dB or more. To the first order of approximation we can include the combined fading margin in algorithm and still allow frequency reuse. The idea is that for every received signal strength in radio there is a distance estimate of the source of the signal. Of course the accuracy of the estimate is affected by the fading.

Address \ channels	C1	C2	C3
A	-	Da	-
B	-	Db	-
C	-	N/A	-
D	-	Dd	-

Where C1, C2, & C3 are channels, and A, B,C, and D are four radios within the sounding domain.

The power management algorithm is not aware of the two dimensional positions of the radios. Through the sounding at full power and ALE message exchange relative distance estimate of neighbors can be maintained at radio C as shown above.

Link Establishment in Contention Period

Assume that channel C2 is silent and not reused, and radio A uses the channel to call radio B following the ALE procedure with the following modifications. In this period of time radio A gain access in a contention situation, and this period is called as "contention period". Based on the radio distance matrix maintained at radio A, it determine a maximum power P_0 for the linkage, and estimate a time period T_0 during which radios A and B will engage in non audible conversation. It may go through a series of training bits in the RTS, CTS, and ACK messages to find P_0 . Command sequence with User Unique Function (UUF) as orderwire message can be used for this purpose (refers to Table A-XV of STD 188-141A). The interaction can be shown in the following drawings.

Contention Free period by NAV

Maximum power P_0 and time period T_0 forms the Network Allocation Vector $NAV(P_0, T_0)$. This $NAV(P_0, T_0)$ is included in the ACK broadcast at full power so that other radios (C and D) can hear it and make a note. During the T_0 period, radio A and B are engaged in non audible conversation. All other radios will avoid full power calls or sounding. This period is called "contention free period" because there will be no contention from other compatible radios.

Frequency Reuse Request in Polled Period

At the end of period T_0 during a short period of G_0 , radio A will find out whether there is any "reuse request". If there is none, radio A will broadcast a continue ACK (CACK) with a new $NAV(P_0', T_0)$. The second P_0' may be different from the initial power which can be estimated from an adaptive tracking algorithm as demonstrated in our previous paper [1]. In order to handle PTT voice with finite buffer, this G_0 period and the following CACK should be as minimal as possible. Having NAV is a compromise to introduce contention free period to handle PTT voice essentially without restriction as in a regular radio (able to continue NAV indefinitely). Furthermore, NAV broadcast with maximal power at pre scheduled time will allows a new party to come onto channel for "frequency reuse".

If radio C wants to contact radio D and find out that all channels are occupied. The determination of occupied channel is based on both silent channel and the last NAV broadcast on the channel. If channels are not occupied, radio C will follows HF ALE procedure to rank the channels according to LQA score just as in MILSTD 188-141A. Let us assume that after finding out all channels are busy, radio C will reuse channel C2 to contact radio D. Based on the sounding relative distance matrix, radio C knows that it is D_a distance away from A.

Based on the $NAV(P_0, T_0)$ broadcast on channel 2 there is a maximum power P_0 corresponding to a domain D_0 around radio A having radio B in range. Since radio D is at a distance D_d which is out of the range of radio A. Radio C decided that it will use power P_2

corresponding to D2 domain shown above for communication. Radio C has to wait to the end of the contention period T_0 and broadcast a reuse request (RR) during the G_0 period following the contention free period.

Because there may be multiple reuse requests in the G_0 contention period, reuse requests are coordinated by the radio possessing the contention free period (radio A). Essentially at the end of the contention free period radio A calls a "ANY RR" message, and participating radios in the net (radio C) respond in the preset time slot. The polling ended with a CACK from A followed by broadcasting NAV(Po', To). Once reuse request (RR) is announced by radio C it can start to engage in non audible conversation with radio D. The NAV(P2, T2) announced by radio C will lock out its own contention free period from cochannel interference.

Assumable Point Control Function

When a channel is silent without any reuse, the access to channel is done in the same way as ALE protocol. Once the channel is used, the radio gaining the channel (radio A) will assume a point control function to coordinate reuse of the channel. It will announce contention free period usage and allows channel reuse request (RR) in the polled contention period. If radio A lost transmission, other radios will time

out contention free period T_0 in the NAV vector and regain the channel back to the normal contention period. The channel changes from normal contention period to contention free period and to polled contention period in turns. In contention period access is coordinated by distributed control algorithm just like that of the ALE protocol. In contention free period the radio gaining the channel employs point control algorithm for frequency reuse. The requirement is that radios will have enough buffer capacity to handle PTT voice during G_0 period. Sounding can only occur in the contention period with full power, and should avoid contention free period and the polled contention period G_0 . Radios in the power management system should keep track of the NAV announcement in the channel. The T_0 in NAV(Po, To) will be decremented according to the clock. Silent channel can be determined from the past NAV vectors kept in the memory. Messages in contention period or polled contention period are announced with full power. Furthermore, radiation in contention free period is done with minimum power so that conversation parties are not interfering with each others. NAV announcement plays a important role to guarantee contention free period without mutual interference.

Advantage of Frequency Reuse

We used two pairs of radios operated at 300MHz with 9600 Baud rate. The packet has

1024 bits, which were generated at one packet per second rate. The initial transmitted power is 0.1 microwatts for both transmitters. The network configuration is shown in Figure 1. Two mobile transmitters are 3.5 Km from the receivers and traveling at 36 Miles/hr speed. The receivers are 1.5 Km apart. Because Tx1 is too close to Rx2, without power control the throughput of Rx2 broke down.

When power control was applied to both transmitters, cochannel interference between them was reduced. Both Tx1 and Tx2 were able to pass packets in a short burst. BER and throughput of both receivers are shown in Figure 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 1. Two Mobile Radio Pairs in Proximity

Figure 2. BER of Rx1 versus Simulation Time

Conclusion

A Protocol for frequency reuse is presented here. The key relies on network allocation vector (NAV) and assumable point control function. Preliminary results of the advantages of frequency reuse are also presented.

Figure 3. Ave. Packet Throughput vs. Time

Figure 4. BER of Rx1 versus Simulation Time

Figure 5. Ave. Throughput of Rx2 vs. Time

References

1. C. H. Lee, "RF Link Power Control with Field Test Data", Proc. Asiloma Conference on Signals, System, & Computers, Nov. 3-6, 1996.
2. MILSTD 188-141A.